

ABSTRACT BOOK

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*SCIENCE-BASED SOLUTIONS IN TIMES OF CRISIS: INTEGRATING SCIENCE
AND POLICY FOR ENVIRONMENTAL CHALLENGES.*

by zearalenone in the second filial generation might mainly be attributed to the decline in *mes-4* expression observed across three generations.

In conclusion, these findings emphasize the significance of zearalenone-induced trans-generational toxicological effects on reproduction and linked epigenetic alterations. We hypothesize that zearalenone disrupted epigenetic regulation in the parental generation, resulting in abnormal epigenetic inheritance across generations, ultimately leading to declined transcription levels of *mes-4* until the second filial generation. Moreover, the lack of *mes-4* led to reproductive defects, contributing to trans-generational effects.

1.06.P-We028 Aquatic neurotoxins – Multi-parametric Analysis of Saxitoxins Effects on *Daphnia magna*

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Saxitoxin and its derivatives are potent natural aquatic neurotoxins produced by certain cyanobacteria and marine algae species during harmful cyanobacterial and algal blooms. These harmful bloom events and the toxins produced during these events are a human and environmental health concern worldwide. Indeed, their occurrence, frequency and severity is predicted to keep increasing due to ongoing climate change scenarios. Saxitoxins constitute an interesting case study since they are produced by both freshwater and marine phytoplankton species, meaning that exposure to these toxins may occur in both aquatic compartments. Despite saxitoxins human health impacts being the focus of extensive research over the past years, adverse effects on other biota and particularly in the aquatic biota are still largely unexplored. This work aims at evaluating the effects of exposures of the model cladoceran *Daphnia magna* to an environmentally relevant concentration of saxitoxin (30 µg/L), that also corresponds to the safety guideline established by the World Health Organization (WHO) for these toxins in recreational freshwaters. Saxitoxin toxic effects were assessed through a comprehensive array of physiological (heart rate), neurotoxicity (total cholinesterases activity), biochemical (antioxidant enzymes activity and lipid peroxidation) and epigenetic biomarkers (5-mC global DNA methylation). Saxitoxin exposure resulted in decreased heart rate, total cholinesterases activity and catalase activity. Contrarily, other antioxidant enzymes, namely glutathione-S-transferases and selenium-dependent glutathione-peroxidase had their activity increased, together with lipid peroxidation levels. Global DNA 5-mC level was significantly decreased in exposed organisms. Results showed that even an ecologically relevant concentration of saxitoxin may cause changes on the antioxidants defenses, leading to oxidative stress, as well as significant physiological impairments and epigenetic alterations in *D. magna* individuals. This study highlights effects on critical molecular and cellular pathways caused by saxitoxin in *Daphnia*, suggesting that these toxins may represent a marked challenge to their thriving even at a concentration deemed safe for humans by the WHO.

1.06.P-We029 EPIBOOST: A Project Aiming to Link Epigenetic Changes to Phenotypic Outcomes in Microalgae, Microcrustaceans and Fish

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Epigenetics has been providing robust and reliable biomarkers for human health diagnosis and therapy, but this step is still largely unexplored in Ecological Risk Assessment (ERA). Many shortcomings contribute to this scenario, including the scarcity of comprehensive functional genomics information on ecotoxicological models, the still short standardization of assessment protocols, the budget required to run epigenomic studies, or, importantly, the need to establish consistent links between epigenetic modifications and downstream effects, primarily gene expression and then phenotypic impairment, allowing reliable extrapolations at larger ecological scales. This link is the focus of the EPIBOOST project, a Twinning Horizon Europe Action. The research component of the project aims to advance knowledge on global and gene-specific DNA methylation changes induced by legacy and emergent aquatic contaminants, using a metal, an antibiotic and a neurotoxin as model chemicals. Furthermore, it extends towards assessing the consequent gene expression changes and phenotypic effects, ranging from the sub-cellular to the population level, concerning specific (e.g. photosynthetic efficiency, neurotoxicity) and more general (e.g. growth rates, behavior) responses to stress. This integrated assessment framework is applied to freshwater and marine microalgae, microcrustaceans and fish, allowing comparative approaches between environmental compartments and different organisms within compartment for a given stressor. Such comprehensive framework will ultimately allow a meaningful insight on the adverse outcome pathways for the selected contaminants, and particularly support the validation of epigenetic modifications as biomarkers of relevance in supporting ERA. As a Twinning Action, EPIBOOST is also strongly dedicated to training. A large group of researchers are being trained hands-on through the research course, but many opportunities have been also created for external researchers and students through the development of Advanced Courses, Summer Schools and Workshops dedicated to transferring scientific and technical/technological knowledge in the field of environmental epigenetics.

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A Project Aiming to Link Epigenetic Changes to Phenotypic Outcomes in Microalgae, Microcrustaceans and Fish

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CONTEXT

- Epigenetics has the potential of providing reliable biomarkers for Ecological Risk Assessment (**ERA**).
- **Epigenetic modifications** are reliable and stable, likely primary Molecular Initiating Events (**MIE**) in Adverse Outcome Pathways (**AOP**) as per their role in constraining **gene expression**.
- The incorporation of epigenomics into regulatory frameworks through AOP refining is challenging as consistent links to effects at the level of the phenotype are yet largely to be established, as well as are trends and parallels across species.
- EPIBOOST is a Twinning Action focusing on the advanced training of researchers in environmental epigenetics towards its integration in ERA. It specifically addresses **DNA methylation changes** in model **freshwater and marine organisms** (microalgae, microcrustaceans and fish) exposed to three model chemicals that represent persistent or emerging threats nowadays or in the near future (**metals, PPCPs and toxins**).
- Besides allowing hands-on training through the development of a focused research project, EPIBOOST has been providing numerous training and dissemination opportunities to a broader interested audience, with a special emphasis on early-career researchers, to nurture, seed and grow the field for the future.

EPIBOOST OVERVIEW

- Twinning project, coordinated by an Institution in a Widening country (University of Aveiro) and having CSIC and the University of Ghent as Advanced partners supporting the leveraging of excellence in environmental epigenetics.
- Essentially a capacitation project focused on training towards excellence, concerning **research**, but also science management and administration.
- Entails a research project: **Responses of model organisms to relevant environmental contaminants**.

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PROGRESS • RESEARCH PROJECT

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